

Achieving Prescribed Performance for Uncertain Impulsive Systems in Brunovsky Canonical Form*

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Abstract—In this work we consider uncertain impulsive systems in Brunovsky canonical form with possibly aperiodic impulses. Following the prescribed performance control methodology, a state feedback controller is designed to guarantee that between any two consecutive impulses, the output tracking error will converge to a neighborhood of zero of predefined size, in no greater than a user selected fixed-time. In addition, all signals in the closed-loop are bounded. Simulations clarify and verify the approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

There has been a significant amount of interest in the field of impulsive systems in recent years. Their applications span many areas, including robotics [2], [23], reset systems [22], industrial electronics [24] and network control systems (NCSs) [20].

The stability analysis of impulsive systems constitutes a significant challenge due to the presence of both continuous and discontinuous dynamics [13]. A lot of effort has gone into ensuring input-to-state stability (ISS) by deriving conditions on the dynamics of the controlled system, on the impulsive characteristics, and the admissible control inputs [10], [11], [15], [18], [21].

Constructive solutions to the problem that propose specific control schemes have also been reported. Particularly, for linear systems with known dynamics, input-output finite-time stability is achieved in [1], while in [9] asymptotic stability is guaranteed.

In the context of nonlinear systems, the difficulties become even more pronounced. Uniform exponential stability is enforced in [16], presenting a user defined convergence rate. Exponential stability is also guaranteed in [14]; however the specifics of the actual exponential response cannot be predetermined. Furthermore, both works consider either fully known or partially known system dynamics respectively. The latter is a strong assumption, as in reality the opposite is rather the case. An attempt to provide a solution for uncertain nonlinear impulsive systems is provided in [19], which achieves asymptotic stability, utilizing neural networks to compensate for the uncertainty in the system dynamics. Nevertheless, the validity of the results depends on the closed-loop states evolving within a compact set where the approximation properties of the neural network are maintained. Given the impulsive behavior of the system,

this is a formidable challenge. Furthermore, solutions that incorporate approximation structures (e.g., neural networks, fuzzy systems), result in increased complexity, as additional differential equations must be solved for parameter derivation, and complex calculations are required to generate the control effort.

Permitting the user to pre-define performance-related control objectives e.g., maximum overshoot, minimum convergence rate, maximum steady state error etc., is highly significant in applications. Yet, this type of task is typically overlooked. The problem magnifies significantly in the light of uncertainty in the controlled system dynamics and the derivation of a low complexity control solutions.

Outside the class of impulsive nonlinear systems, the prescribed performance control (PPC) methodology has been developed to operate within the framework under consideration. The method was originally proposed in [3] and consequently utilized to provide control solutions for various classes of uncertain nonlinear systems (see indicatively [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [26]). In an attempt to provide prescribed performance attributes for nonlinear uncertain systems when the tracking reference signal is discontinuous using PPC, an impulsive closed-loop system was formulated in [12]. Nevertheless, the impulses did not appear at the state of the system. A valid solution to the aforementioned problem was provided in [17], for the class of Euler-Lagrange.

In this work, we extend the results of [17] by designing a controller, following the PPC methodology, for impulsive systems in Brunovsky canonical form, having locally Lipschitz nonlinearities with unknown analytical expressions. The impulsive sequence can be aperiodic and the difference between any two consecutive impulsive time instances should be longer than a known lower bound. Yet, the exact impulse time instants are unknown. The proposed controller guarantees that between any two consecutive impulses, the output tracking error will converge to a neighborhood of zero of predefined size, in no greater than a user-selected fixed time. Nevertheless, all signals in the closed-loop remain bounded. In addition, no hard calculations (analytic or numerical) are required to produce the control signal, thus formulating a low-complexity control solution.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. In Section II we formulate the problem. We present the main results in Section III. We provide the proof of the main theorem of this work in Section IV. To clarify and verify the theoretical findings, we perform simulations, which are provided in Section V. Finally, we conclude in Section VI.

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II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a SISO nonlinear impulsive system in Brunovsky canonical form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{x}_i(t) &= x_{i+1}(t), \quad i = 1, \dots, n-1, \\ \dot{x}_n(t) &= f(\bar{x}(t)) + g(\bar{x}(t))u(t) + d(t) \end{aligned} \right\} t \notin \mathbb{J},$$

$$x_i(t) = x_i(t^-) + \Delta x_i(k), \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (1)$$

$$y = x_1,$$

where $\bar{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ represent the state of the system with $x_i(t_0) = x_i^0$, $i = 1, \dots, n$ being the initial conditions, $u \in \mathbb{R}$ is the control input, $d \in \mathbb{R}$ represents piecewise continuous and bounded external disturbances and $y \in \mathbb{R}$ is the system's output. Furthermore, $f, g \in \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are unknown, locally Lipschitz functions. $\mathbb{J} = \{t_k : k \in \mathbb{N}_+\}$, short for $\{t_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_+}$ represents the set of impulse sequence.

Assumption 1: The sign of $g(\bar{x})$ is either strictly negative or strictly positive and it is considered known; without loss of generality it is assumed positive.

Assumption 2: The impulse sequences satisfy $t_{k+1} - t_k \geq \bar{\tau} > 0$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, where $\bar{\tau}$ is known. However, the exact impulse time instants are unknown. Moreover, the impulses $\Delta x_i(k)$ are bounded.

Assumption 3: The desired trajectory $y_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ and its first order derivative \dot{y}_d are continuous and bounded. However, \dot{y}_d is considered unknown and y_d is available only at each time instant; y_d is considered unknown in advance.

Control Objective: Consider the nonlinear impulsive Control Objective system (1) satisfying Assumptions 1, 2. Consider also the output reference signal $y_d(t)$ satisfying Assumption 3 and the corresponding output tracking error $e_1 = x_1 - y_d$. Design a controller to guarantee that a) $|e_1(t)|$ will be strictly less than a prespecified value $\delta_1 > 0$ for all $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$, $\tau < \bar{\tau}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ where $\tau > 0$ is a predefined fixed time; b) all signals in the closed loop are bounded.

III. MAIN RESULTS

The following theorem, whose proof is presented in Section IV, summarize the main result of this work.

Theorem 1: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (1) and Assumptions 1-3. Let τ be a prespecified time instant satisfying $\bar{\tau} > \tau > 0$ and $\delta_1 > 0$ is a given constant. Define $e_1 = x_1 - y_d$. Given any initial conditions $\bar{x}(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and for all $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the control law:

$$a_0 = y_d, \quad (2a)$$

$$\xi_i = \frac{x_i - a_{i-1}}{\rho_i} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2b)$$

$$a_i = -k_i T(\xi_i)^3 - k'_i T(\xi_i) \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2c)$$

$$u = a_n \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2d)$$

where

$$\rho_i(t) = (\rho_i^k - \rho_i^\infty) e^{-\lambda_i^k(t-t_k)} + \rho_i^\infty, \quad t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}), \quad (2e)$$

$$\rho_i(t) = \rho_i(t^-) + \Delta \rho_i(k), \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (2f)$$

$$\Delta \rho_i(k) = \beta_i |\Delta x_i(k)| + \beta'_i |\Delta a_{i-1}(k)|, \quad (2g)$$

$$\Delta a_{i-1,j}(k) = a_{i-1,j}(t) - a_{i-1,j}(t^-), \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (2h)$$

with $k_i, k'_i > 0$, $\beta_i, \beta'_i > 1$, $T : (-1, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $T(z) = \ln((1+z)/(1-z))$ and

$$\lambda_i^k > \ln\left(\frac{\rho_i^k - \rho_i^\infty}{\delta_i - \rho_i^\infty}\right) / \tau, \quad \rho_i^k \geq \rho_i^\infty > 0, \quad \rho_i^\infty < \delta_i, \quad (2i)$$

$$\rho_i^0 \equiv \rho_i(t_0) > |x_i(t_0) - a_{i-1}(t_0)|, \quad \rho_i^k = \rho_i(t_k), \quad (2j)$$

guarantees:

- 1) $|e_1(t)| < \delta_1, \forall t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$;
- 2) the boundedness of all signals in the closed loop.

Remark 1: The proposed controller (2) is of low-complexity since i) no hard calculations (analytic or numerical) are required; ii) no a priori knowledge of the actual system nonlinearities are required, not even some corresponding bounds or bounding functions; iii) no approximating structures i.e., neural networks or fuzzy systems are incorporated to acquire such knowledge; iv) the controller is static.

Remark 2: The impulsive dynamics (1), (2f) define an event triggering mechanism; as soon as an impulse appears at the time instant t_k , $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, the jumps indicated by (1), (2f) simultaneously take place. Therefore, the time instants t_k are a priori unknown.

Remark 3: Regarding the construction of the performance functions, we stress that the desired performance on $e_1(t)$ are solely introduced in the closed-loop system via the output performance functions $\rho_1(t)$. Specifically, given the performance parameters δ_1, τ and the initial conditions $\bar{x}(t_0)$, then utilizing the (2i), (2j), the selection of ρ_1^∞ and λ_1^k , $k \in \mathbb{N}$ can be made to construct $\rho_1(t)$. This leads to enforcing the performance requirements stated in the control objective. All other ρ_j functions $j = 2, \dots, n$, together with k_i, k'_i, β_i and β'_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, are control elements which can be freely chosen provided (2i), (2j) are satisfied and $k_i, k'_i > 0$, $\beta_i, \beta'_i > 1$. However, it should be noted that simulation studies indicate that their selection affects the evolution of e_1 inside the performance envelope defined by ρ_1 , as well as the requested control effort (magnitude and slew-rate). Specifically, utilizing a more aggressive strategy, large λ_i^k and control gains k_i, k'_i , small ρ_i^∞, β_i and β'_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, typically results in producing larger control input values during transient, while demonstrating satisfying performance at steady state. On the other hand, small λ_i^k and control gains k_i, k'_i , high-valued ρ_i^∞, β_i and β'_i , lead to improved transient behaviour and oscillatory-steady state behaviour. Therefore, the selection of the control elements is application-driven and cannot be predetermined. However, carefully selected design parameters may positively influence the evolution of $e_1(t)$, as well as the magnitude and slew-rate of the produced control effort.

IV. PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Differentiating (2b) with respect to time, we obtain

$$\dot{\xi}_i = \frac{1}{\rho_i} [\xi_{i+1} \rho_{i+1} + a_i - \dot{a}_{i-1} - \xi_i \dot{\rho}_i], \quad (3a)$$

$$\dot{\xi}_n = \frac{1}{\rho_n} [f(\bar{x}) + g(\bar{x})u_i + d(t) - \dot{a}_{n-1} - \xi_n \dot{\rho}_n]. \quad (3b)$$

Define $\xi = [\xi_1, \dots, \xi_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and

$$\dot{\xi} = h(\xi, t) = [h_1, \dots, h_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad (4)$$

where the h -functions are the right-hand sides of (3).

Additionally, let us define the open set $\Omega_\xi = (-1, 1)^n \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. To prove Theorem 1, it is sufficient to show that controller (2), guarantees that the functions $T(\xi_i)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$, appearing in (2c) and (2d) remain bounded. Owing to T being strictly increasing, the latter is equivalent to proving that ξ evolves strictly within a subset of Ω_ξ for all $t \geq 0$. Thus, all closed-loop signals ξ_i, a_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ will remain bounded, with $a_n = u$.

The proof of Theorem 1 consists of two lemmas. In Lemma 1, prescribe performance characteristics are enforced $\forall t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$. Lemma 2, proves the boundedness of all closed-loop signals.

Lemma 1: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (1) and Assumptions 1-3. Controller (2) guarantees that $|e_1(t)| < \delta_1$, for all $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof: The proof of this lemma consists of three phases. First, a unique maximal solution $\xi(t)$ of (4) over the set Ω_ξ is obtained for a time interval $[t_0, \tau_{max})$, with $\tau_{max} \leq t_1$. Then, in the second phase we extend the τ_{max} to t_1 . Finally, in the third phase the extension of the aforementioned results for all time intervals $[t_k, t_{k+1})$, $k \geq 2$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is accomplished.

Phase A: The set Ω_ξ is open and non-empty. Also the performance functions $\rho_i(t_0)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$ are selected so that $\xi(t_0) \in \Omega_\xi$. Therefore, there exists a unique maximal solution of $\xi(t)$ in $[t_0, \tau_{max})$, with $\tau_{max} \in [t_0, t_1]$.

Phase B: Owing to the results of Phase A, we conclude that $\xi_i \in (-1, 1)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Therefore,

$$\epsilon_i \triangleq T(\xi_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

are well-defined for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. The rest of the analysis for Phase B follows a recursive n -step procedure.

Step 1: Define the positive definite function

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_1^2. \quad (6)$$

Differentiating (6) with respect to time and using (3a) we obtain:

$$\dot{V}_1 = \frac{\epsilon_1}{\rho_1} \frac{dT}{d\xi_1} (\xi_2 \rho_2 - k_1 \epsilon_1^3 - k'_1 \epsilon_1 - \dot{a}_0 - \xi_1 \dot{\rho}_1). \quad (7)$$

Notice that $dT/d\xi_1 > 0$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$, since $\xi \in (-1, 1)^n$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$ and $\rho_i > 0$ for all $t \geq t_0$. Furthermore, since $a_0 = y_d$, differentiating it with respect to time, yields $\dot{a}_0 = \dot{y}_d$, which is bounded owing to Assumption 3. Also, ρ_2 and $\dot{\rho}_1$ are bounded by construction. Additionally, define $F_1 = |\xi_2 \rho_2| + |\dot{y}_d| + |\xi_1 \dot{\rho}_1| > 0$. Using

the aforementioned arguments, we conclude the existence of positive constant \bar{F}_1 , such that $F_1 \leq \bar{F}_1$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Define $\phi_i = (dT/d\xi_i)/\rho_i$. Thus, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1 &\leq \phi_1 (\bar{F}_1 \epsilon_1 - k_1 \epsilon_1^4 - k'_1 \epsilon_1^2) \\ &\leq \phi_1 (\bar{F}_1^2/k'_1 - k_1 \epsilon_1^4). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Consequently, $\dot{V}_1 < 0$ when $|\epsilon_1| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/k'_1 k_1}$. Therefore, $|\epsilon_1| \leq \bar{\epsilon}_1 \triangleq \max\{|\epsilon_1(t_0)|, \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/k'_1 k_1}\}$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Using the inverse logarithmic function we obtain:

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\bar{\epsilon}_1) \leq \xi_1 \leq T^{-1}(\bar{\epsilon}_1) < 1. \quad (9)$$

Additionally, notice that owing to the continuity of h_1 in (4), there exist positive constant \bar{h}_1 such that satisfy $|h_1| \leq \bar{h}_1$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. The latter and (2c) lead to the conclusion that $|\dot{a}_1|$ is bounded.

Step i ($2 \leq i \leq n-1$): Define the positive definite function $V_i = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_i^2$. Following the same line of analysis as in Step 1, we obtain the existence of positive constants \bar{F}_i such that $|\epsilon_i| \leq \bar{\epsilon}_i = \max\{|\epsilon_i(t_0)|, \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_i^2/k'_i k_i}\}$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Thereafter, using the inverse logarithmic function, we derive

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\bar{\epsilon}_i) \leq \xi_i \leq T^{-1}(\bar{\epsilon}_i) < 1 \quad (10)$$

for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$, $i = 2, \dots, n-1$ and the boundedness of $|\dot{a}_i|$.

Step n: Define the positive definite function

$$V_n = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_n^2. \quad (11)$$

Differentiating (11) with respect to time and using (3b) we obtain:

$$\dot{V}_n = \frac{\epsilon_n}{\rho_n} \frac{dT}{d\xi_n} (f(\bar{x}) - g(\bar{x})(k_n \epsilon_n^3 + k'_n \epsilon_n) - \dot{a}_{n-1} - \xi_n \dot{\rho}_n). \quad (12)$$

Owing to the continuity of f, g application of the Extreme Value Theorem and Assumption 1 guarantees the existence of positive constants \bar{f}, \bar{g}, g , such that $|f(\bar{x})| \leq \bar{f}$ and $0 < g \leq g(\bar{x}) \leq \bar{g}$. Additionally, the external disturbance is bounded by definition. Therefore, defining $F_n = |f(\bar{x})| + |d(t)| + |\dot{a}_{n-1}| + |\xi_n \dot{\rho}_n| > 0$, and using the aforementioned arguments, we conclude the existence of positive constants \bar{F}_n , such that $F_n \leq \bar{F}_n$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Thus, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_n &\leq \phi_n |g(\bar{x})| (\bar{F}_n \epsilon_n / g - k_n \epsilon_n^4 - k'_n \epsilon_n^2) \\ &\leq \phi_n |g(\bar{x})| (\bar{F}_n^2 / (g^2 k'_n) - k_n \epsilon_n^4) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Consequently, $\dot{V}_n < 0$ when $|\epsilon_n| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_n^2 / (g^2 k'_n k_n)}$. Therefore, $|\epsilon_n| \leq \bar{\epsilon}_n \triangleq \max\{|\epsilon_n(t_0)|, \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_n^2 / (g^2 k'_n k_n)}\}$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Using the inverse logarithmic function we conclude that:

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\bar{\epsilon}_n) \leq \xi_n \leq T^{-1}(\bar{\epsilon}_n) < 1. \quad (14)$$

Finally, from (9), (10) and (14), we conclude that ξ evolves strictly with a compact subset of $\Omega'_{\xi_k} \subset \Omega_\xi$, where Ω'_{ξ_k} depends on \bar{F}_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$. Hence, all states x_i , the intermediate signals a_i , $i = 1, \dots, n-1$ and the control law u are bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. At this point, using standard arguments [25], we extend τ_{max} to t_1 .

Phase C: In this phase we will present that if $\xi(t_1^-) \in \Omega_\xi$ then $\xi(t_1) \in \Omega_\xi$ as well. By continuity of y_d and owing to (2h), we obtain $\Delta a_0 = y_d(t_k) - y_d(t_k^-) = 0$. Then, owing to $|\xi_i(t_1^-)| < 1$ we have

$$-\rho_i(t_1^-) < x_i(t_1^-) - a_{i-1}(t_1^-) < \rho_i(t_1^-). \quad (15)$$

Using (2g), (2g) and the definitions of $\Delta\rho_i(k)$, $\Delta x_i(k)$, $\Delta a_i(k)$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & -\rho_i(t_1) + \beta_i|\Delta x_i(1)| + \beta'_i|\Delta a_{i-1}(1)| \\ & < x_i(t_1) - \Delta x_i(1) - a_{i-1}(t_1) + \Delta a_{i-1}(1) \\ & < \rho_i(t_1) - \beta_i|\Delta x_i(1)| - \beta'_i|\Delta a_{i-1}(1)| \\ & -\rho_i(t_1) + \beta_i|\Delta x_i(1)| + \Delta x_i(1) + \beta'_i|\Delta a_{i-1}(1)| \\ & - \Delta a_{i-1}(1) < x_i(t_1) - a_{i-1}(t_1) < \rho_i(t_1) \\ & - \beta_i|\Delta x_i(1)| + \Delta x_i(1) - \beta'_i|\Delta a_{i-1}(1)| - \Delta a_{i-1}(1). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$(17)$$

As $\beta_i, \beta'_i > 1$, we conclude $\beta_i|\Delta x_i(1)| + \Delta x_i(1) + \beta'_i|\Delta a_{i-1}(1)| - \Delta a_{i-1}(1) > 0$ and $-\beta_i|\Delta x_i(1)| + \Delta x_i(1) - \beta'_i|\Delta a_{i-1}(1)| - \Delta a_{i-1}(1) < 0$. Therefore,

$$-\rho_i(t_1) < x_i(t_1) - a_{i-1}(t_1) < \rho_i(t_1), \quad (18)$$

and $\xi(t_1) \in \Omega_\xi$.

The line of proof of phases A, B, C can be repeated recursively for all time intervals $[t_k, t_{k+1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, thus proving Lemma 1.

Thus far we proved that $\xi(t)$ evolves strictly within Ω'_{ξ_k} for all $t = [t_k, t_{k+1})$, whose size differ at each time interval owing to their dependency on \bar{F}_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, which in turn depend on the bounds of ξ_i, ρ_i at t_k and we still have not shown that these bounds are non-increasing with respect to k . Therefore, the boundedness of all closed loop signals is still open. In that respect, owing to Assumption 2, the energy induced at every impulse is bounded. Hence, we need to show that $V_i(t_k)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$ are bounded. The latter is guaranteed provided that $V_i(t_k^-)$ are bounded by constants independent of $V_i(t_{k-1})$. This is the objective of Lemma 2.

Lemma 2: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (1) and Assumptions 1-3. Controller (2) guarantees the boundedness of a_i, x_i and that $\xi_i \in (-1, 1)$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Proof: The proof of this lemma consists of n steps.

Step 1: From (8) we concluded:

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq \frac{\phi_1}{k'_1}(\bar{F}_1^2 - k'_1 k_1 \epsilon_1^4), \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1).$$

Hence, there exists a constant $l_1 > 0$ such that

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq -\frac{\phi_1}{k'_1} l_1 \epsilon_1^4, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1),$$

provided that $|\epsilon_1| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$. Additionally, utilizing the strictly increasing property of T and the definition of $\rho_i(t)$, we obtain

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq -\frac{2}{\rho_1^\infty k'_1} l_1 \epsilon_1^4, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1).$$

Defining the constant $l'_1 \triangleq 2l_1/\rho_1^\infty k'_1$ and utilizing the definition of V_1 we conclude that:

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq -4l'_1 V_1^2, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1), \quad (19)$$

provided that $|\epsilon_1| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$. To continue, we distinguish two cases.

Case 1 ($|\epsilon_1| \leq \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$): We proved that \dot{V}_1 is negative when $|\epsilon_1| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$. Therefore, $\sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$ is the upper bound of $|\epsilon_1|$ for all $t \in [t_0, t_1)$. As a result, $\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$ is the upper bound of V_1 for all $t \in [t_0, t_1)$.

Case 2 ($|\epsilon_1| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$): By the continuity of ϵ_1 , there exists a time constant $t'_1 \leq t_1$ such that $|\epsilon_1| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{F}_1^2/(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}$, for all $t \in [t_0, t'_1)$. Therefore, integrating (19) yields

$$V_1 \leq \frac{V_1(t_0)}{4l'_1 V_1(t_0)(t - t_0) + 1}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t'_1).$$

If $t'_1 < t_1$ then the same arguments as in Case 1 apply for all $t \in [t'_1, t_1)$. Therefore, aggregating both cases we obtain that for all $t \in [t_0, t_1)$

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \left\{ \frac{V_1(t_0)}{4l'_1 V_1(t_0)(t - t_0) + 1}, \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{F}_1^2}{(k'_1 k_1 - l_1)}} \right\}. \quad (20)$$

Consequently, utilizing Assumption 2, we have

$$V_1(t_1^-) \leq \bar{V}_1 = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{4l'_1 \bar{\tau}}, \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{F}_1^2}{(k_1^2 - l_1)}} \right\}. \quad (21)$$

Define $E_1(k)$ the energy injected to V_1 when $t \in \mathbb{J}$. Then owing to Assumption 2, $E_1(k)$ is bounded for all $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$. Hence, $V_1(t_1) = V_1(t_1^-) + E_1(1) \leq \bar{V}_1 + E_1(1)$. Then

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \{V_1(t_0), V_1(t_1^-) + E_1(1)\}. \quad (22)$$

Therefore by induction, we obtain for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \geq 2$

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(t_k) &= V_1(t_k^-) + E_1(k) \leq \bar{V}_1 + E_1(k), \\ V_1(t) &\leq \max \{ \bar{V}_1 + E_1(k-1), \bar{V}_1 + E_1(k) \}, \forall t \in [t_{k-1}, t_k]. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$(24)$$

Aggregating all time intervals, yields

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \{V_1(t_0), \bar{V}_1 + E_1(1), \dots, \bar{V}_1 + E_1(k)\}, \forall t \geq t_0. \quad (25)$$

Hence, since \bar{V}_1 and $V_1(t_0)$ are bounded independently of k and $E_1(k)$ is bounded, we obtain that $V_1(t)$ is bounded for

all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$, which leads to the boundedness of $\epsilon_1(t)$ and $a_1(t)$. Additionally, denoting the ultimate bound of $|\epsilon_1(t)|$ as γ_1 , we obtain for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\gamma_1) \leq \xi_1(t) \leq T^{-1}(\gamma_1) < 1. \quad (26)$$

Therefore, $x_1(t)$ is bounded and owing to (2g), $\rho_1(t)$ is also bounded.

Step j ($j = 2, \dots, n$): We follow the same analysis as in step 1 and we conclude that $V_j(t)$ is bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$. Consequently, $\epsilon_j(t)$, $a_j(t)$, $\rho_j(t)$ and $x_j(t)$ are bounded, with $a_n(t) = u(t)$.

V. SIMULATION

To demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed controller, we present simulations performed on a single-link robotic manipulator actuated by a brush DC (BDC) benchmark problem. Denoting with q , \dot{q} , \ddot{q} the link position, velocity and acceleration respectively, the systems dynamics are:

$$\begin{aligned} M\ddot{q} &= g\sin(q) - C\dot{q} + wI \\ L\dot{I} &= -RI - K\dot{q} + 2u, \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where I [A] is the motor's armature current and u [V] is the control input voltage. The system parameters are assumed to be: $M = 0.5$ [Nm s^2 /rad], $g = 9.81$ [Nm], $C = 1$ [Nm s /rad], $2 = 1$ [Nm/A], $L = 0.05$ [H], $R = 0.5$ [Ω] and $K = 10$ [Nm/A]. The state of the system is $\bar{x} = [q \ \dot{q} \ I]^T \in \mathbb{R}^e$. Initially the system is at $\bar{x}(0) = [pi/6 \ 0 \ 0]^T$.

The reference signal to be tracked is $y_d(t) = \pi\sin(\pi t)/6 + \pi/9$. It is desired, the output tracking error $e_1(t)$ to converge not later than the fixed time $\tau = 3s$ to the interior of the set $\{e_1 \in \mathbb{R} : |e_1(t)| \leq \pi/45\}$. Therefore we set $\delta_1 = \pi/45$. System (27) is subject to impulses satisfying $t_{k+1} - t_k \geq \bar{\tau} = 4$. We assume that three impulses occur at $t_1 = 5s$, $t_2 = 10s$ and $t_2 = 15s$. Particularly, at $t_1 = 5s$ a spike of strength $\Delta x_1(1) = \pi/12$ affects q . Then, a second spike occurs at $t_2 = 10s$ with strength $\Delta x_2(2) = -\pi/12$ affecting \dot{q} , and finally at $t_1 = 15s$ the impulse affects both q and \dot{q} with strengths $\Delta x_1(3) = -\pi/12$ and $\Delta x_2(3) = \pi/12$. To achieve smooth state evolution with reasonable control effort, all other control elements were selected accordingly to Theorem 1 as $k_1 = 0.15$, $k'_1 = 0.15$, $k_i = 12$, $k'_i = 0.15$, $i = 2, 3$, $\delta_2 = \pi/18$, $\delta_2 = 3$, $\rho_1 = 0.3067e^{-t} + 0.0524$, $\rho_2 = 0.6004e^{-t} + 0.0873$, $\rho_3 = 24.2908e^{-1.0734t} + 2$, $\beta_i = 4$ and $\beta'_i = 1.1$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$.

The results are pictured in Figs. 1-3. Specifically, in Fig 1 the state of the system is plotted, and the achievement of output tracking is illustrated. In Fig 2, the output error $q - y_d$ along with the intermediate errors $\dot{q} - a_1$, $I - a_2$ are presented. All aforementioned errors evolve strictly within the performance bounds as Theorem 1 predicts. Finally, in Fig 3, the requested control effort is pictured, clearly showing it is reasonably bounded despite the presence of the impulses.

Fig. 1. Evolution of the states (blue lines) along with the desired trajectory (black line).

Fig. 2. Evolution of the output tracking error $e_1 = q - y_d$ and the intermediate errors $e_2 = \dot{q} - a_1$, $e_3 = I - a_2$ alongside with their corresponding performance bounds and the required control effort.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the required control effort.

VI. CONCLUSION

We considered the problem of controlling uncertain impulsive systems in Brunovsky canonical form with possibly aperiodic impulses. The proposed controller solution guaranteed that between any two consecutive impulses, the output tracking error will converge to a neighborhood of zero of predefined size, in no greater than a user-defined fixed-time. Moreover, all signals in the closed-loop were proven bounded. The theoretical findings were illustrated with the help of simulations.

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